

Assessment of the Impact of Poaching on Aquatic Wildlife in the Vicinity of the Douala-Edéa National Park (Cameroon-West Africa)

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Abstract

The poaching of marine megafauna is poorly documented in Cameroon, and the existing data do not allow for the establishment of a reliable management strategy. Therefore, the characterization of poaching of aquatic wildlife in the Kribi 2nd, Lokoundjé, and Edéa 1st districts was carried out with the aim of contributing to the fight against this threat. To this end, structured and semi-structured surveys, as well as direct observations, were conducted by collecting data at 3 markets, 11 restaurants, and Sedan households in the area. Both qualitative and quantitative aspects were noted regarding the actors, targeted species, and costs.

The Student's t-test allowed for a distribution according to the seasons and ANOVA to compare the acquisition methods. The results show that 88% of households are supplied by men while women handle distribution in the markets (90%) and in restaurants (67%). These actors, mostly Cameroonians (58.8%) aged between 21 and 40, catch an average of 33 ± 4 sea turtles per year, preferentially during the dry season ($p < 0.05$), collect 1620 ± 32 sea turtle eggs each year, dolphins (1/year), manatees (8/year); as well as monitor lizards and crocodiles, boa constrictors and pythons, though the figures are indeterminate, especially during the rainy season.

Sea turtle eggs are collected from nests at nesting sites, turtles are also gathered after strandings in nets, and manatees are hunted with harpoons. In restaurants, the meat of sea turtles is sold for about 5.72 ± 0.53 € and manatees for $3.8 \pm$ € per piece. For sustainable management of these species, it would be advisable to establish alternatives such as the farming of grass cutter and ecotourism within these local communities.

Keywords: Poaching, Characterization, Ecotourism, Aquatic Fauna, Edéa 1st, Kribi 2nd, and Lokoundjé.

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1. Introduction

The increase in demand for wild aquatic meat is seen as a growing threat to aquatic wildlife in many parts of the world (Robards et al., 2011). In some areas, there is evidence showing that the opportunistic use of accidentally captured animals has turned into targeted catches (Clapham et al., 2007). Over the years, the anthropogenic threat to species classified at different levels of vulnerability has been increasing. It is becoming increasingly important to implement a system for managing marine biological resources in various environments.

Facing an exponentially growing population, this resource is insufficient to meet the demand for animal protein from fishery sources. To address this deficit, the population in these areas resorts to poaching to ensure its food security (Cosentino et al., 2016). In addition to nutritional needs, some populations living near marine and coastal areas resort to poaching for cultural or medicinal purposes (Cosentino et al., 2016). Manatees, dolphins, and sea turtles found in the Gulf of Guinea, specifically along the Cameroonian coast, are subject to the same constraints (Powel, 1996) and deserve special attention.

Although there is relatively abundant documentation on sea turtles, it is difficult to determine the scale and impact of the trade in other aquatic bushmeat, as much of the meat processing occurs illegally, either at sea or far from centralized food markets. On the other hand, research has so far focused on documenting prevalence, rather than assessing the impact on species and populations. There is an urgent need to develop methods to evaluate the impact of this type of aquatic bushmeat exploitation in order to better understand the issue and establish priorities. For many species, the mortality rate is higher than previously estimated, and concerns are greater on the Cameroonian coast, where a specific characterization of poaching activities on aquatic wildlife has not yet been conducted.

Thus, this study aims to provide the necessary baseline to establish a management system on the outskirts of the Douala-Edéa National Park and especially along the borders of the cities of Kribi and Edéa, which are the main selling points. The overall objective of this study is to assess the impact of poaching in aquatic environments in the localities of Edéa 1st, Kribi 2nd, and Lokoundjé, and to make proposals for the sustainable management of these species. Specifically, the focus will be on:

- Characterize poaching of aquatic wildlife (collection areas, actors...);
- Determine the targeted species in these localities and the marketing circuits according to the seasons;
- Suggest recommendations for the sustainable management of these species.

2. General Information on Poaching

The hunting for meat from wild animals poses a significant and immediate threat to the future of wildlife in many regions around the world (Brashares et al., 2004). Efforts made to date in general

policy have mainly focused on terrestrial bushmeat; thus, although the concept of bushmeat extended to aquatic wild fauna was introduced several years ago (Van Waerebeek et al., 2002), it has not yet received sufficient attention, given the scope of the issue. New evidence shows the existence of a conservation problem on a scale similar to that documented for terrestrial bushmeat, currently affecting species belonging to aquatic wildlife, including cetaceans, sirenians, sea turtles, crocodiles, and even seabirds.

2.1 Poaching in Aquatic Environments

2.1.1 Target Species Targeted by Poaching in Aquatic Environments

A large number of countries in West and Central Africa host extensive coastal communities with limited protein supplies, which have expanded over the last few decades as populations migrate from other regions to coastal areas in search of employment. There is evidence of the use of small cetaceans in most countries in the region; their meat and organs are used for food and as bait for sharks. Ghana is responsible for most of the captures in West Africa: 16 species of cetaceans are affected and more than a thousand animals are landed each year (Debrah et al., 2010; Ofori-Danson et al., 2003; Van Waerebeek et al., 2009 & 2014). Thus, the species most affected in Ghana during the period 1998-2010 were (in descending order): the Clymene dolphin (*Stenella clymene*), the Spotted dolphin (*Stenella attenuata*), and the common bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*). Other important affected species include the tropical pilot whale (*Globicephala macrorhynchus*) and a species of common dolphin (*Delphinus capensis*). Nine other species were occasionally landed (<5% for each species) (Debrah et al., 2010; Van Waerebeek et al., 2014).

Dolphins are caught as bycatch in drifting gillnet fishing and sometimes in other fisheries, but targeted catches are also found. In some cases, the meat is used as bait for sharks and contributes to the economic viability of shark fishing (Ofori-Danson et al., 2003; Weir et al., 2008; Van Waerebeek et al., 2009 & 2014; Debrah et al., 2010). Recent data from several countries in the region show that cetaceans are regularly consumed, as in Togo (Segniagbeto et al., 2014), in Benin (Sohou et al., 2013), to Nigeria (Uwagbae et al., 2010), and to Cameroon (Ayissi et al., 2014).

2.1.2 Actors of Poaching in Aquatic Environments

The poaching of sea turtles in the western Indian Ocean, particularly in Kenya (Nzuki, 2005), in Madagascar, and Mozambique (Louro et al., 2012), seems to be carried out primarily by local fishermen. In the southwest of Madagascar, in particular, targeted harvests of sea turtles are well documented, despite national decrees prohibiting their exploitation. Poaching at sea appears to be increasing in other parts of the country due to accidental and intentional catches on a local and international scale (Muttenger, 2007; Gough et al., 2009). There is little information on the harvesting of sea turtles in the northern Indian Ocean. It is believed that Olive Ridley turtles have been targeted by fishermen for their meat in the Sundarbans, Cox's Bazar, while a decrease in egg collection has been observed (Hasan, 2009). Most information concerning India is anecdotal and based on arrests.

Egg collection is extremely significant in certain places; for example, almost all Olive Ridley turtle nests located along a part of the Tamil Nadu coastline had been subject to poaching during the nesting season from January to April, and it appears that such practices continue (Rajakruna et al., 2009). Surveys show that up to 62% of village populations along the southern and western coast may consume turtle meat and eggs (Rajakruna et al., 2009). Along the west coast, a butchering and over-the-air sale of live turtles has been observed (Kapurusinghe, 2006).

In the Comoros, green turtles and hawksbill turtles captured by local fishermen are most often consumed or sold, and rarely released. Widespread poaching of sea turtles was observed in the Moheli Marine Park in 2009. In Kenya, it is estimated that 10 to 50% of the sea turtles nesting on the beaches, as well as their nests, are subjected to poaching and are sold on black markets (Nzuki, 2004). An illegal trade was reported at the back of the houses and fish markets (Zanre, 2005). About 10% of turtle by-products in Tana Delta and Malindi were provided by foreign fishermen, most of whom come from Somalia and Tanzania (Nzuki, 2005).

In Tanzania, egg collection persists, even though ecotourism programs may have a positive effect (Ferraro, 2007). Similarly, another study showed that accidental catches of turtles by fisheries in this same area amounted to approximately 3,656 turtles per year (Frontier-Madagascar, 2003). In 2003, the sale of turtle meat was considered common, involving an integrated chain of fishermen, intermediaries, and traders (Walker et al., 2004); in 2011, however, marine turtle products had proportionally decreased in curiosity markets (Gibbons et al., 2011). Poaching has been confirmed in northern Madagascar, with 40% of green turtles and hawksbill turtles captured being consumed or sold (Poonian et al., unpublished).

In January 2012, a significant trafficking of plastron (tortoise shell) was reported, leading to the arrest of five individuals (Hamitra, 2012). It is estimated that up to 40kg of sea turtle has been transported to Toliara each week. A new smuggling network was also discovered in North Western Madagascar in 2012, supplying merchants in Mahajanga, although the final destination has not been identified. There are concerns about the extent of poaching in Mozambique, based on observations of discarded turtle shells along the beaches, even though this poaching has not been quantified (Louro et al., 2012; Williams, 2012). The meat of the sea turtle was once shared for free among the villagers (Pascal, 2008), but it was reported in 2013 that fishing had become commercial (Stein-Rostaing, 2013). In Tanzania, a study showed that turtle-derived products were being sold freely and illegally at the main landing sites in Dar Es Salaam (West, 2008).

A study conducted by Bobo et al. (2015) showed that in the East of Cameroon, poaching of terrestrial animals is conducted 74% by the Konabembe Bantu, 12% by the Pygmies, 6% by the rest of the Bantu community, and foreigners from the Central African Republic only account for 1%. The local communities are therefore predominantly responsible for the pressure on biodiversity, whether terrestrial or aquatic.

2.1.3 Uses of Aquatic Bushmeat Catches

Hunting for bushmeat intended for illegal local trade poses a serious threat to marine crocodiles (*Crocodylus porosus*), and the crocodiles from the 'biodiversity hotspot' region of Indo-Myanmar are particularly vulnerable (Meganathan et al., 2010; Meganathan et al., 2013; Velho et al., 2012). The poaching of sea turtles in the Coral Triangle region (Southeast Asia) seems to be on the rise (Lam et al., 2011), intended for trade in China and Vietnam. In addition to the intentional captures of turtles, it is estimated that 4,000 turtles are captured each year along the coasts of Vietnam as bycatch (Hamann et al., 2006). It is also estimated that around 1,115 green turtles (*Chelonia mydas*) are illegally captured each year in southeastern Sulawesi; in 2001, this region was undoubtedly the main exploitation site for the hawksbill turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricata*).

In Malaysia, there is evidence of substantial egg harvesting in Sabah, Terengganu, and Rantau Abang. In fact, the collection of leatherback turtle (*Dermochelys coriacea*) eggs at Rantau Abang has undoubtedly led to a decline in the number of nests, going from 10,000 nests per year to only 3 in 2002 (Troeng et al., 2004). In the Philippines, nearly 70% of the eggs laid on the Tawi-Tawi islands were harvested in the past (Chan et al., 2002), and these collections continued until recently. In Papua New Guinea, the collection of leatherback turtle eggs was a common practice along the Huon coasts until recently (Kinch, 2006). Anecdotal reports suggest that illegal egg collection is still practiced along the coasts of Myanmar (Win et al., 2012), despite a decline in nesting.

It has been reported that Chinese turtle poachers (mainly in Hainan province) have turned to Malaysian waters for their supply of whole turtles (Lam et al., 2011). Green turtles and hawksbill turtles captured by fishermen in the waters of the Philippines appear to be sold directly to Chinese buyers in southern China and the Sulu Sea, in order to avoid inspections (Lam et al., 2011). Following a large-scale contraction of the wholesale export market to Vietnam resulting from a ban imposed by law in 2002, several reports have indicated that most Vietnamese tortoise catches are now being sold directly at sea, in exchange for products purchased on board ships coming from Hainan (Chan et al., 2009). The large number of seizures made in Vietnam, including hawksbill turtles, suggests that Indonesia and Malaysia could still be a source of raw scales used in the production of Bekko (turtle shell).

Supplied by people from other regions of Indonesia (particularly Southeast Sulawesi and Java), and intended to primarily supply national markets, but also to satisfy international demand (Troeng et al., 2004). Although the annual volume of turtle trade, previously estimated at several tens of thousands of animals, seems to have decreased significantly in recent years, the national trade supplying restaurants in Bali continued to thrive in 2012. In 2013, a trade in live green turtles rather than processed meat was reported, camouflaged in an attempt to evade detection by law enforcement authorities (Jakarta Post, 2013).

In Malaysian Borneo, freely sold eggs without any control have been reported in Sabah and Sarawak, even though these two states prohibit egg collection. On the other hand, a number of seizures made in recent years have helped to better understand how the illicit trade operates. In

Peninsular Malaysia, Terengganu has historically been regarded as an important center for the egg trade, with eggs imported partly from neighboring countries and other Malaysian states where egg collection is illegal – attracting buyers who sometimes come from Indonesia.

2.1.4 Consumption of Product from Poaching

There is a long history of exploiting aquatic animals for food and non-food purposes in Asia. More recently, bycatch has become a targeted and commercial hunt for cetaceans and sirenians (Tun, 2006; Clapham et al., 2007). Although there is little documented information on the extent and impact of the use of aquatic bushmeat in South and Southeast Asia, the decline of dugongs has been attributed to their hunting (Heinsohn et al., 2004; Marsh et al., 2004; Mustika, 2006).

2.1.5 Capture Method of Species

Certain catch data for non-selective fisheries, such as the 'experimental nets' used in South Asia, show that single sets of nets can capture several thousand cetaceans, including Mysticetes, which are subsequently used for human consumption and in the pet food industry. Beyond active hunting and collection, aquatic bushmeat is obtained from accidental catches. Accidental catches in fisheries refer to the capture of non-target species and concern marine, brackish, and freshwater megafauna, notably mammals, sea turtles, seabirds, crocodiles, etc. Some countries engage in well-known small cetacean hunting and have catch data, although the impact on local populations is not known. Since the few available data show a decline in populations and large-scale catches by fisheries suggests that the impact on cetacean and sirenian populations is significant. As for the eggs of sea turtles, local residents conduct daytime and nighttime patrols to collect the eggs laid in nests on targeted nesting beaches (Troeng et al., 2004).

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Presentation of the Study Area

3.1.1 Geographic Location

The study covers the districts of Edéa 1st, Kribi 2nd, and Lokoundjé located in the Ocean Departments, South Cameroon Region, and Sanaga Maritime, Littoral Region, respectively. This area covers an area of 11,280 km² and its geographical coordinates are between 2°8' and 3°35' North latitude and 9°49' and 11°11' East longitude, with a coastline of 75 km (Sayer et al., 1992). It is limited to the West by the Atlantic Ocean, the Arrondissements of Mouanko and Dizangue, to the North by Edéa 2nd, to the South by Kribi 1st, and to the East by Nyété. The figure below shows the area of our study.

Figure 1: Map of our study area (@INC, 2013 modified by Fogwan 2017).

3.1.2 Pedology and Topography

Two types of soils are observed in this area. Red ferralitic soils whose parent rock is acid with a homogeneous aspect. Yellow ferralitic soils whose parent rocks are respectively gneiss and mica schists, which occupy most of the region. They present a sandy-clay texture on the surface, clay-sandy or clayey at depth, under the effect of intense leaching. The altitude varies from 0 to 50 meters and the highest point is at an altitude of 120 meters (Kramkimel et al., 1987).

3.1.3 Hydrology

The hydrographic network is vast and composed of important rivers, most of which source from the southern Cameroon plateau. The Kienké drains the entire city of Kribi. It has a length of 130 km and an average flow of 49.2 m³/s. The Lobé with its panoramic tourist waterfalls located 10 km from the city of Kribi; the Lokoundjé, and the Ntem, which serves as a natural border with Equatorial Guinea in southern Cameroon. All flow into the Atlantic Ocean (Olivry, 1986).

3.1.4 Climate

This coastal area is part of the equatorial climate zone and the classic Guinean domain. It offers two main climates, the interior Guinean climate and the maritime climate, influenced respectively by the proximity to the sea and by continentality. There are two seasons: a long rainy season, which lasts for eight months (from March to October) with precipitation above 1900 mm, and a short dry season (from November to February) with precipitation below 160 mm. The winds are brisk (11 km/h) due to the proximity of the Atlantic Ocean. Heavy rainfall is recorded in September (683 mm) while the hottest month is March (28.5°C). Rainfall is lower in December, and August is the coldest month (24°C).

3.1.5 Flora

The flora in this area is primarily composed of microphytes, mangroves, and coastal forests. It is distributed as follows: the Atlantic coastal forest with Caesalpiniaceae, the periodically flooded swamp forest of the low valleys of the Sanaga with *Uapaca* spp, the periodically flooded swamp forest behind the mangrove, with *Guibourtia demeusei* and *Oxystigma manni*. Another part consists of the forest on sandy coastal ridges, with *Saccoglottis gabonensis* and *Klainedoxa microphylla* on sand, *Anthostema aubryanum* and *Ctenolophus nengleranus* on mud. The tall outer mangroves are composed of *Rhizophora racemosa* and *Pandanus candelabrum* along the estuary. Other swamp plants such as *Nypa fruticans* and *Pandanus candelabrum* are also noted (Letouzey, 1985).

3.1.6 Fauna

We distinguish between the aerial predatory fauna of aquatic species and the terrestrial fauna composed of reptiles and mammals. The aquatic fauna is represented by fish, crustaceans (crabs, shrimp), mollusks, and amphibians. The reptiles mainly consist of four species: sea turtles that are increasingly subjected to anthropogenic pressure (Ayissi, 2015), Nile crocodiles, boa constrictors, and monitor lizards. Freshwater turtles can be found in the creeks of Nyong and Lokoundjé. The marine mammals inhabiting this area are represented by small cetaceans (*Sousa teuszii*, *Tursiops truncatus*) and sirenians, with the species *Trichechus senegalensis* dominating the estuarine waters of the Nyong and Lokoundjé.

3.1.7 Human Environment and Socio-Economic Activities

The Kribi 2nd, Lokoundjé, and Edéa 1st Districts have an estimated population of 93,246 people (BUCREP, 2005). The main activities in the area include fishing, sand extraction, agriculture, timber harvesting, hunting, and oil exploitation. The vast majority of the local population primarily relies on fishing for their livelihood. Some engage in subsistence farming on alluvial soils. River fishing is mainly focused on fish and clams. Commercial hunting is carried out by the Bassa and Ewondo communities, targeting monkeys and ruminants. Except for immigrants, there are about ten indigenous ethnic groups, including the Batanga (the majority in the area), Mabi, Bakoko, Ewondo, and Fang.

3.2 Data Collection

3.2.1 Secondary Data

Secondary data is primarily sourced from documents found in the libraries of ACBM (Cameroonian Association for the Promotion of Marine Biology), IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature), WWF (World Wildlife Fund), and other technical services of MINFOF

(Ministry of Forests and Wildlife), as well as on websites. The data on the quantities of seized aquatic origin meats will be obtained from forest control posts.

3.2.2 Primary Data

The collection of primary data involved both qualitative and quantitative data. The data were obtained from observations and surveys conducted with households, restaurants, fishermen, public services, as well as in the local markets. A total of 25 households, 3 markets, and 11 restaurants made up the sample for this study. The information collected was primarily based on:

- Characterization of the actors through the collection of individual data on the age, sex, and nationality of each stakeholder.
- Determination of the targeted species which were recorded through direct observations and surveys, along with the seasons of abundance and method of acquisition.
- Collection areas and marketing circuits which refer to the different collection sites and frequencies of marketing, thus the markets which are the drop-off points, as well as the selling prices of the species sold.

3.3 Statistical Analyses

The Excel spreadsheet was used to perform descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) and to construct the graphs. The SPSS version 16.0 software was used to conduct the Student's t-test to determine the dependence between the proportions of each species and the seasons of capture. Similarly, it was used to perform ANOVA between the capture methods. When there were significant differences among the sources of variation, the Duncan test at the 5% level was used to separate the means.

4. Results

4.1 Characterization of the Actors Involved in Aquatic Wildlife Poaching

4.1.1 Distribution of Actors by Sex and Age

It appears that aquatic wildlife poaching and related activities affect both men and women. Households are supplied by men (88%), while distribution is mainly handled by women, 90% in restaurants and 67% in markets. Young people aged 21 to 40 are more affected, regardless of the sector of intervention. However, in markets, the 31 to 40 age group dominates at 64.3%. Restaurants are run by the same age group at 54.5%, while household consumption affects all age groups. The figure opposite illustrates the distribution of actors by sex and age according to the sectors of intervention.

Figure 2: Distribution by sex a) and age b) of actors according to the sectors of intervention

4-1-2-Distribution by Nationality

This distribution shows that people of three main nationalities exert pressure on protected aquatic animals. These are Cameroonians, responsible for 58.8% of household consumption and the entire marketing network. The remaining household consumers are divided between Nigerians (35.3%) and Ghanaians (5.9%). The figure below shows the distribution of stakeholders by nationality.

Figure 3: Distribution of actors by nationality

4-2-Species Targeted by Poaching

4-2-1-Abundance of Targeted Species

Poaching activity targeting aquatic wildlife targets seven species, including sea turtles, dolphins, manatees, monitor lizards, boa constrictors, crocodiles, and sea turtle eggs, corresponding to six species of wild aquatic wildlife. The pressure is greatest on turtle eggs, with $1,620 \pm 325$ eggs consumed in households each year. However, they are not found on the local market or in restaurants. However, 27 ± 3 sea turtles and 8 ± 0 manatees are captured each year for household consumption, for a total of 33 sea turtles and 10 manatees per year. Crocodiles, on the other hand, are found on the market and in restaurants at weekly frequencies of 15 ± 4 and 23 ± 7 , respectively.

Table 1: Abundance of aquatic species subject to poaching.

	Sea turtle	Dolphin	Manatee	Varan	python	Crocodile	Turtle eggs
Number in household	27 ± 3	1 ± 0	8 ± 0	3 ± 0	6 ± 1	156 ± 55	1620 ± 325
Number in restaurants/week	$5 \pm 1/\text{an}$	0	$2 \pm 0/\text{an}$	17 ± 4	10 ± 2	23 ± 7	0
Number in markets/week	1	0	0	7 ± 2	0	15 ± 4	0

Values are presented as mean \pm standard deviation

4-2-2-Seasonal variations in targets

However, 27 ± 3 sea turtles and 8 ± 0 manatees are captured each year for household consumption, for a total of 33 sea turtles and 10 manatees per year. Crocodiles, on the other hand, are found in the market and in restaurants at weekly frequencies of 15 ± 4 and 23 ± 7 , respectively. The figure below shows the seasonal variations in the proportions of target species.

Figure 4: Seasonal variations of target species a) Marine species b) Terrestrial species

This figure shows that the number of sea turtles killed and consumed is significantly ($p < 0.05$) high in the dry season, while the proportions of manatees and dolphins are independent of the seasons. Regarding crocodiles and monitor lizards, the quantities taken from the wild are significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the rainy season, at 21 and 10 per week, respectively. All sea turtle eggs are collected in the dry season, from October to April, during the nesting season.

4-2-3 Capture Methods for Targeted Species

The species targeted by aquatic wildlife poaching are acquired through six different methods. These include the collection of packaged discards, accidental captures, collection after stranding, gathering, the use of traps, and active hunting. These methods are diverse for sea turtles and consistent for other species. The proportion of sea turtles collected after stranding is significantly lower ($p < 0.05$), 14.3%, than that obtained following packaged discards (42.9% and accidental captures (42.9%). The figure below shows the proportions of species according to their method of acquisition. The figure below shows the canoe and harpoon, which are gear used for manatee hunting.

Figure 5: Gears used for manatee hunting: a) Canoe and b) harpoon

4-3-Collection Areas and Marketing Channels

4-3-1-Collection Areas

It appears that poaching products destined for the area's markets come from six hubs and are not evenly distributed. The Nyong locality provides 72.2% of crocodiles, 72.7% of monitor lizards, and 16.7% of sea turtles. Lokoundjé provides all manatees, Dizangue provides 63.6% of boa constrictors, Mouanko 11.1% of crocodiles, and Kribi and Campo provide 50% and 33.3% of sea turtles, respectively.

4-3-2-Sales Costs

The selling price varies from one species to another for the end consumer. In markets and restaurants, these species are sold in price ranges ranging from 2.97 ± 0.48 € for the sea turtle to 5.72 ± 0.53 € for the monitor lizard. The manatee ranks second with 3.8 ± 0.38 €. The figure below shows the variation in selling prices of products from aquatic poaching by species.

4-4-Discussion

4-4-1-Poaching Actors

Poaching actors in aquatic environments in Edea 1st, Kribi 2nd, and Lokoundjé are distributed according to the intervention sectors. While households are supplied by men, women handle marketing. These activities mainly involve Cameroonians and Nigerians aged 21 to 40. Some characteristics are similar to those described by Bobo et al. (2015) on poaching in forest areas in eastern Cameroon. In forest areas, poachers are of both sexes, young, and predominantly indigenous. Regarding this practice in aquatic environments, the distribution of activities is likely due to the organization of this coastal population. These resources are mainly exploited by local residents due to easy access due to proximity.

4-4-2-Targeted Species

Regarding targeted species, preferences appear to be oriented toward species with high nutritional value or species whose consumption is linked to local customs. In terms of quantity, sea turtle eggs are the most popular in households, with $1,620 \pm 325$ eggs consumed per year, obtained by collection following patrols of nesting sites, mostly during the dry season. This result corroborates that of WWF (2005) and shows that sea turtle eggs are subject to a high poaching rate on the Asian coasts. The acquisition method is the same as that described by Troeng and Drews (2004) in West Africa and South America. The poaching season for sea turtle eggs is believed to be closely linked to the nesting period on the Cameroonian coast, which corresponds to the months from October to May (Ayissi, 2015).

The average total number of sea turtles caught is significantly high in the dry season and this species is obtained by collecting packaged discards and accidental captures. The nesting season would correspond to a period during which sea turtles are found in maritime and industrial artisanal fishing areas. These fishermen, both industrial and artisanal, would therefore use fishing gear that is non-selective or not very selective for sea turtles that accidentally end up in the nets. Given the surveillance in the maritime environment, industrialists choose the option of packaging their catches and releasing them into the environment. These turtles would therefore be collected dead or alive by local residents and intended for consumption or trade. The method of acquisition of sea turtles by poachers on the coast is similar to that observed in Madagascar Gough et al. (2009). They demonstrated that in this country, sea turtle poaching is increasing due to accidental captures, as is the case on the Cameroonian coast, but also due to intentional captures, which are rare in

Cameroon. Local residents reportedly do not have the appropriate technology for active sea turtle hunting.

Manatees, dolphins, crocodiles, monitor lizards, and boa constrictors are intentionally hunted using harpoons, traps, and barriers. This practice, carried out during the rainy season, is thought to contribute to flooding in the Sanaga, Nyong, and Lokoundje valleys, which reduces access to other food resources and promotes the proximity of aquatic species. Ayissi (2014) demonstrated that dolphins were captured in Campo (Cameroon) for consumption. This corroborates the results of Clapham and Van Waerebeek (2007). However, the capture methods are not the same as those described by CMS (2015), which specifies that the targets are caught in nets. This could be explained by the archaic nature of the local technology used for this purpose.

4-4-3-Collection Areas and Marketing Channels

The species affected by aquatic wildlife poaching are collected throughout Cameroon's coastline and sold in markets and specialty restaurants. Selling prices range from 2.97 ± 0.48 € to 5.72 ± 0.53 €. These prices are higher than those recorded by Bobo et al. (2015), who show that primates poached in the eastern Cameroonian forest cost 2.51 € in restaurants. These high costs are believed to be due to the rarity and high nutritional value of aquatic products.

Conclusion

The study conducted to characterize aquatic wildlife poaching in Edea 1st, Kribi 2nd, and Lokoundjé revealed that the key players are young people aged 31 to 40, 64.29% in markets and 54.55% in restaurants, and all ages in households. They are of both sexes and predominantly indigenous. The main target species are sea turtle eggs ($1,620 \pm 325$ /year). Sea turtles, manatees, dolphins, crocodiles, boa constrictors, and monitor lizards are also targeted by harvesting methods ranging from collecting turtle eggs to accidental capture of sea turtles and hunting for other species. Sea turtles and eggs are collected during the dry season, while other species are collected during the rainy season. The efforts of this practice are rewarded by sales, the prices of which vary depending on the species, from 2.97 ± 0.48 € to 5.72 ± 0.53 €. Thus, poaching of aquatic wildlife is subject to seasonal fluctuations, and the method differs from one species to another.

Recommendations

Several recommendations were made to improve knowledge of poaching and better protect aquatic wildlife through a significant reduction in the trade, capture, consumption, and other uses of coastal and marine species, including endangered, threatened, or protected aquatic species.

• Ecological Recommendations

Fishermen should release accidentally captured turtles without packaging them to ensure the continuation of their life cycle. In addition, indigenous peoples should develop alternative income-

generating activities to poaching, such as fish farming and the production of crabs or snails for consumption and marketing.

• Scientific Recommendations

Researchers should:

- Conduct a characterization of the value chain to assess the benefits of each stakeholder, useful for developing alternative activities;
- Extend such a study to the entire Cameroonian coastline to establish national priorities.

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